

administered graded doses of the test compound in the form of gum acacia suspension, intraperitoneally. The mortality of mice in each group was recorded during the next 24 h for the purpose of calculating LD₅₀ value.

Antimicrobial activity: The antibacterial activity of the compounds was assayed against two bacteria, *Pseudomonas ovalis* and *Bacillus megaterium*, at 100 µg ml⁻¹ concentration by the filter paper disc method¹¹. They were also screened for their antifungal activity by a standard method¹² against two phytopathogenic fungi, *Curvularia lunata* and *Dreschlera rostrata* at a concentration of 250 µg ml⁻¹. Bavistin, a commercial fungicide was employed as a standard.

Analgesic and antiinflammatory activities: The analgesic and antiinflammatory activities of the compounds were determined by standard methods¹³⁻¹⁵ at a dose of 100 mg/kg body weight using albino mice and rats, respectively. Aspirin and phenylbutazone were employed as standards.

The results of all these investigations are presented in Table 2.

It was encouraging to note that all the ten compounds were non-toxic even at a dose of 1200 mg/kg body weight. Perusal of Table 2 reveals that compound 7 was more effective against both the bacteria, followed by compound 8. Compounds 10, 5, 6 and 1 were found to be moderate bactericides. Compound 5 was proved to be a potential fungicide as it could cause total inhibition of both the fungi, followed by compounds 6 and 7. All the compounds were shown to be superior over the commercial fungicide, Bavistin.

Compound 4 with phenylacetamido moiety exhibited a notable analgesic and antiinflammatory activities and almost it excelled aspirin. A moderate analgesic activity of compounds 8, 3, 6 and 1 was also recorded. All the compounds exhibited reasonable antiinflammatory activity which was superior over that of phenylbutazone.

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Synthesis of 2-Aminonicotinaldehyde Hydrazones as Possible Antimicrobial Agents

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A good deal of importance is being given to hydrazones due to their wide use as antibacterial¹⁻³, antifungal⁴, insecticidal^{5,6}, hypoglycemic⁷, amoebicidal⁸ and antiinflammatory⁹ agents. Some of the hydrazones have also been found to possess antitubercular¹⁰ property. Isonicotinic acid hydrazide is found superior to some other pyridine and non-pyridine hydrazides towards tuberculostatic activity¹¹. With a view to reduce toxicity due to free amino group, the condensation products of a number of hydrazides with various aldehydes and ketones were also examined¹². Taking into account the varied activities exhibited by hydrazones, a series of hitherto unknown hydrazones derived from 2-aminonicotinaldehyde have been made in the present investigation.

The compounds described in this communication have been synthesised by the condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde with different aliphatic, aromatic and heteroaromatic acid hydrazides in ethanol in the presence of a trace of glacial acetic acid. Relatively higher yields were obtained when the reaction was conducted in dry benzene and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid. The purity and homogeneity of all the compounds were tested by tlc and elemental analysis.

The structures of these compounds have been established by a combination of elemental analyses (Table I) and spectral (ir, mass and pmr) data. The ir spectra of these hydrazones showed the characteristic bands at 3400, 3250 (NH₂), 3150 (NH), 1660 (amide carbonyl), 1600 (C=C or C=N), 1570, 1460, 1380, 1240, 1080, 980 and 900 cm⁻¹. The

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF HYDRAZONES

Sl. no.	R	M p.	Yield	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					O	H	N
1.	Phenyl	282	60	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	64.90 (65.00)	5.03 (5.00)	23.17 (23.33)
2	4-Methylphenyl	240	80	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	66.00 (66.14)	5.45 (5.51)	21.97 (22.05)
3	4-Methoxyphenyl	286	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	62.01 (62.22)	5.07 (5.18)	20.80 (20.74)
4.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	257	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	60.83 (60.94)	4.75 (4.69)	21.81 (21.88)
5.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	291	67	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	60.82 (60.94)	4.71 (4.69)	21.83 (21.88)
6.	2-Chlorophenyl	211	66	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ OCl	56.78 (56.93)	3.90 (4.01)	20.35 (20.44)
7.	3-Chlorophenyl	290	64	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ OCl	56.80 (56.93)	4.00 (4.01)	20.41 (20.44)
8.	4-Chlorophenyl	248	69	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ OCl	56.86 (56.93)	3.95 (4.01)	20.37 (20.44)
9.	3-Nitrophenyl	240	63	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	54.68 (54.74)	3.78 (3.86)	24.39 (24.56)
10	4-Nitrophenyl	214	64	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	54.69 (54.74)	3.75 (3.86)	24.45 (24.56)
11.	3,5-Dinitrophenyl	252	61	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	47.13 (47.27)	3.01 (3.08)	25.29 (25.45)
12.	Phenylvinyl	255	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	67.58 (67.67)	5.21 (5.26)	20.88 (21.05)
13.	3-Pyridyl	300	70	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	59.81 (59.75)	4.48 (4.56)	29.01 (29.05)
14.	4-Pyridyl	247	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	59.88 (59.75)	4.51 (4.56)	29.00 (29.05)
15.	Methyl	249	72	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	53.87 (53.98)	5.58 (5.62)	31.39 (31.46)

mass spectra of hydrazones exhibited strong molecular ion peaks consistent with their elemental analyses. The mass spectra of phenyl and 2-chlorophenylhydrazones showed strong molecular ion peaks at m/z 240 and 274, respectively.

The pmr spectrum of 4-methoxyphenylhydrazone in DMSO- d_6 showed a three-proton singlet at δ 3.8 assignable to methoxyl group. It also exhibited a singlet at δ 8.4 due to $CH=N$. The amide NH resonated as a broad signal at 6.5. The two protons attached to nitrogen appeared at δ 2.45. The remaining seven aromatic protons appeared as a complex multiplet at δ 7.0-8.0.

Experimental

All melting points were taken by open capillary method and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 Infracord spectrophotometer in KBr phase. Pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian 100 MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal reference, and mass spectra on a Varian Mat CH-7 instrument. The physical and analytical data are presented in Table I.

2-Aminonicotinaldehyde and acid hydrazides were prepared by known methods.

Preparation of hydrazones: A mixture of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (0.1 mol) and appropriate acid hydrazide (0.1 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (25-30 ml) in the presence of a few drops of glacial acetic acid on a steam bath for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the separated solid was filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallised from ethanol (Table I).

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H-2', H-5', H-6'), 6.78 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.52 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 5.42 (1H, dd, J 9, 2 Hz, H-2), 2.80 (2H, m, two H-3) and 2.30 (12H, br, 4 phenolic acetoxy). It was identified as (-) eriodictyol and the identity was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample. It is the first report of its isolation from this genus.

Compound B: Elutions with 10% EtOAc in C_6H_6 afforded this compound and it was crystallised from EtOAc- C_6H_6 (120 mg), m.p. 327-29°; gave brown colour with ferric chloride and pink colour with Mg/HCl; ν_{max} (KBr) 1650 (CO) and 3300 cm^{-1} (OH); acetate δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.60 (2H, br, H-2', H-6'), 7.20 (3H, br, H-5', H-3, H-8), 6.80 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6) and 2.25 (12H, s, 4 phenolic acetoxy). These data suggest compound B to be luteolin and the identity was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample. This is the first report of its isolation from this genus.

Compound C: It was obtained from elutions with 10% EtOAc in C_6H_6 and crystallised from EtOAc- C_6H_6 (2 g), m.p. 238-40°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ (MeOH); colour reactions suggested a flavonoid skeleton; ν_{max} (KBr) 1620 (CO) and 3350 cm^{-1} (OH); acetate δ ($CdCl_2$) 7.20 (3H, m, H-2', H-5', H-6'), 6.72 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.52 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 5.60 (1H, d, J 12 Hz, H-2), 5.35 (1H, d, J 12 Hz, H-3), 2.21 (12H, s, 4 phenolic acetoxy) and 1.98 (3H, s, aliphatic acetoxy). These data suggest compound C to be dihydroquercetin and the identity was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Dihydroquercetin has already been reported² in *Pistacia chinensis*.

Chemical Components of *Pistacia integerrima*

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PISTACIA integerrima (Anacardiaceae) is available at Solan, Himachal Pradesh. Its galls, formed on its leaves, by hemipteris, have been reported¹ to have medicinal values against cough, fever, loss of appetite, nose bleeding, vomiting and stomach troubles. Since *P. integerrima* has not been subjected to chemical examination earlier, we have investigated its heartwood obtained from Solan. The plant material (2 kg) was chopped into small pieces and then extracted with hot ethanol. The extractives were column chromatographed over silica gel and three compounds labelled as A, B and C could be isolated and characterised.

Compound A: It was obtained from elutions with 5% EtOAc in C_6H_6 and crystallised from EtOAc- C_6H_6 (100 mg), m.p. 270-72°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ (MeOH); colour reactions indicated flavonoid skeleton; ν_{max} (KBr) 1620 (CO) and 3300 cm^{-1} (OH); acetate (Ac_2O/Py) δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.25 (3H, br,

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